

Rieko Kodama, the First Lady of SEGA – Part Three

Andrés Domenech Alcaide

CoolJapan.es

Do you remember that Rieko Kodama became a key mind behind the Phantasy Star franchise? What happened afterward? And what about Sega? Neither she nor the company stopped there. Sega was still far from its later decline—which, fortunately, did not mean disappearance—and still had much to offer us, including the unforgettable hedgehog, Sonic.

The Golden Era of SEGA: The 1990s

Sega finally achieved what no company had managed against Nintendo since the 1980s: it made a statement and established itself as a true competitor to the Kyoto giant. At that time, following the massive crisis in the U.S. video game industry, Nintendo had taken advantage of the disaster and become the leading console brand. Sega successfully entered the U.S. and European home console markets, building a solid reputation in Japan. It did so with the Mark III of 1985—its version outside Asia was called the Master System—and later the Mega Drive in 1988—known as the Genesis in the U.S.—. Sega already had a significant presence in Japan, though it was more widely known for its arcade machines and game halls—a legacy it still maintains today, along with being one of the most recognisable brands in collectible figures such as prize figures.

But what was Sega missing? A “mascot” for the company. A flagship character... just as Mario is for Nintendo. While Alex Kidd was initially intended for this role, the final choice became the speedy blue hedgehog, Sonic.

So... what does Sonic have to do with Rieko Kodama if this article is about her? Everything! As Rieko Kodama was part of the *Sonic* development team.

She worked alongside Yūji Naka, with whom she had already collaborated on *Phantasy Star*. Kodama had contributed to *Phantasy Star*, but she also worked on other Sega franchises, such as the action game *Altered Beast* (1988), RPGs like *Sorcerian* (1990), and later instalments of *Phantasy Star*, including the second (1989) and fourth (1994) entries.

In *Sonic the Hedgehog* (1991), she was primarily responsible for designing elements of the game related to backgrounds, joining the team when development was already well underway. Naoto Ōshima designed iconic characters such as the protagonist, while Rieko Kodama handled the visual design of the levels and overall game aesthetics. Sonic could roll and move at high speed, both rolling and running, and the team had to coordinate the work of designers and programmers to ensure that the game worlds accommodated this new gameplay dynamic.

Sonic in his first encounter with Dr. Eggman —Ivo Robotnik— during the third act of Green Hill Zone, from the first *Sonic* on Mega Drive/Genesis. Rieko Kodama was one of the people responsible for what you see.

Sonic was a huge success and catapulted Sega to fame, making it the perennial rival to Nintendo throughout the 1990s, right up until Sony entered the market and began vying with both companies... eventually surpassing them by the end of that decade and into the next.

Video games and franchises such as *Streets of Rage* —*Bare Knuckle*, the first released in 1991—, *Golden Axe* (1989), and *The Revenge of Shinobi* —one of the most popular titles in the *Shinobi* series, also from 1989— became widely known both inside and outside Japan. Meanwhile, Kodama returned to *Sonic* for its second instalment, *Sonic the Hedgehog 2* (1992), and also worked on one of Disney's most renowned games: *Castle of Illusion Starring Mickey Mouse* (1990), where she contributed artwork and graphics.

You may now understand why we mentioned the various collections of video games and the miniature versions of the Mega Drive in earlier articles, since both include several titles on which Rieko Kodama worked —we are confident the tribute to the artist on the Mega Drive Mini 2 is now clearer.

The Stellar Fantasy Rises

Phantasy Star continued to grow, and in addition to a Mega Drive version of the first game, it received a second instalment: *Phantasy Star II* (1989), Sega's first 16-bit RPG. It took advantage of the Mega Drive's power to offer higher-quality graphics and music, making effective use of Yamaha's YM2612 sound chip, which was skilfully employed by artists such as Tokuhiko Uwabo and Yūzō Koshiro —both of whom, by the way, have worked with Kodama.

In this second adventure on the Algol system, Kodama worked alongside Ōshima, the character designer from *Sonic*. The story takes on a more mature and complex tone, incorporating dystopian themes and technological conspiracies. It was one of the early games to offer a persistent world that players could revisit across different iterations of the franchise.

The third entry, *Phantasy Star III: Generations of Doom* (1990), did not include Kodama's direct involvement. While it was a good game, —offering decision-making mechanics that influenced narrative outcomes and showcasing generational shifts among characters— gamers missed Kodama's visual style, as it featured more realistic graphics that lacked the distinctiveness and vibrant colour of her designs.

She returned to the development team for the fourth instalment, *Phantasy Star IV: The End of the Millennium* (1993, for Mega Drive). The “IV” in the title was added later for the Western market, because the original development team viewed it not simply as a fourth numbered sequel but as the conclusion of a saga, particularly considering that it sits chronologically between *Phantasy Star II* and *III*.

It offered a striking visual presentation for a console of its era. With large, detailed graphics, polished and fluid animations, it also featured epic battles and a mature storyline, serving as a crowning achievement for the Algol system's saga by creating cohesion across earlier instalments in terms of narrative and thematic depth.

Phantasy Star IV laid the groundwork for persistent and open-world video games —a concept also owed to franchises such as *Ultima* by Richard Garriott—, a legacy that would be built upon by Sega itself years later with titles like *Phantasy Star Online* (released in 2000).

Original cover of *Phantasy Star: The End of the Millennium* —1993—, led by Rieko Kodama. In the centre, the protagonist Chaz Ashley, alongside Rika —right— and Rune Walsh —left—.

The story is accompanied by panels and frames in the purest manga style, and its script is complex and extensive for what a console video game typically offered at the time, serving as Sega's proof that console games could deliver the complexity of personal computer RPGs —something that delighted Kodama herself.

It features the hunter Alys Brangwin —unrelated to the already familiar Alis Landale, as her original name is *Raira* (ライラ)— and her young apprentice, Chaz Ashley, who is also the game's protagonist, alongside a large cast of up to eleven playable characters.

SEGA and the Late-90s Console War

Against Sony, which entered the console market in 1994 with the PlayStation, Nintendo maintained for a while its previously most successful console, the Super Famicom —known in the West as the Super Nintendo Entertainment System (SNES or Super NES)—, which remained competitive until 1996, when the company launched the Nintendo 64. Sega, for its part, released its next console after the Mega Drive, the Sega Saturn, at the very end of 1994, the same year the PlayStation was released in Japan.

However, Sega could not compete with Sony, which stormed the market, undercutting rivals with a lower launch price —including Sega's own Saturn. This contributed to the future decline in Sega's console sales and its eventual cessation of producing new gaming systems, aside from the Mini versions of the Mega Drive developed by Sega in the 2020s.

Was Rieko Kodama involved in any of these Sega Saturn games? Of course —but not as a designer or artist, rather as a producer. *Deep Fear* (1998) was one of Sega's ventures into horror games. With a soundtrack conducted by the renowned Kenji Kawai, the plot revolves around a submarine that mysteriously loses all contact. The protagonists' mission is to discover what happened, which involves supernatural experiences, alien parasites, and the need to explore and defend themselves within a claustrophobic environment. Kodama was one of the producers, alongside Noriyoshi Ōba and Kōichi Satō.

During the 1990s, Kodama also served as director for the Saturn video game *Magic Knight Rayearth* (1995), based on designs by the group of artists and mangaka known as CLAMP. This adaptation is based on the eponymous manga created by them and the anime series adapted from the manga.

This game does not simply offer a single female protagonist —it features three: Hikaru Shidō, Umi Ryūzaki, and Fū Hōōji. The trio is transported to the planet Cephire to lend their aid, and they are informed that they are magical warriors by their summoner, Guru Clef, who serves Princess Emeraude captured by Zagato, her high priest.

This title draws heavily from The Legend of Zelda series, allowing players to control one of the three friends at will —although all three travel together on the adventure—, each with their own weapons and abilities: Hikaru wields a sword, Umi a rapier, and Fū a bow and arrows. The manga itself has a development style very similar to a video game, in which the protagonists gradually acquire new abilities to face increasingly difficult challenges, which facilitated its adaptation.

Illustration of the protagonists of *Magic Knight Rayearth* by the CLAMP team

It was a game that saw both the beginning and almost the end of the Sega Saturn market—it was among the first titles announced for the console in Japan and the last to be released in the United States, in 1998. Seventy-five percent of the Saturn's catalogue was released exclusively in Japan, and this game nearly followed the same fate, as endless delays; including lost code, translations, and animations forced the Western team to reconstruct it as best they could, ultimately releasing it in the West in 1998, the very year the Dreamcast launched.

By this time, at the close of the twentieth century, Rieko Kodama had already made a name for herself in the Japanese video game industry and within Sega itself. Although her name was not attached during those years to major projects in which she participated—such as Sonic—it was linked to a group of “cult” games, much like Igarashi with the Castlevania titles he worked on, gaining fame and recognition for her contributions years later.

What other titles did this remarkable artist bring us before she passed? We will explore them in the next and final entry in our tribute to her!

Sources

- **Texts consulted from:** Eurogamer, Phantasy Star Fandom, Sega Retro, Szczepaniak, J. (2014), *The Untold History of Japanese Game Developers: Volume 1*. SMG Szczepaniak | **Text created by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
- **Images sourced from:** Biblio, SMS Power, Sega Bits, IGN, Sega Retro, Lego

Licence and original publication

- **Licence:** This article and its content are published under **CC BY 4.0**, allowing sharing and adaptation while citing the source and author
- *Originally published on CoolJapan.es on 21 October 2025 —Rieko Kodama, la gran dama de SEGA – Tercera parte—*
- *This version is a faithful translation into English by Andrés Domenech Alcaide*